

ESTIMATION OF GENETIC GAIN FOR PRODUCTION AND REPRODUCTION TRAITS IN HOLSTEIN FRIESIAN CROSSBRED: ASSESSMENT AND SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

Background: The present analysis aimed to investigate the expected genetic gain along with simulation study for productive and reproductive parameters in Karan Fries cattle (Holstein Friesian X Tharparkar) in particular calving to first insemination interval (CFI), 305 day milk yield (305DMY) and Wet average (WA).

Methods: Data on productivity and reproduction features of Karan Fries cattle kept in an organized herd at the ICAR-NDRI, Karnal were exercised throughout 24-year period from 1993 to 2016. Expected genetic gain (ΔG) of 305 DMY, WA and CFI were calculated by utilizing two separate approaches i.e. Approach I ($\Delta G = h^2$) and Approach II ($\Delta G = i\sigma_{ph}^2$) Additionally ΔG was also determined by simulating various parameters viz. selection intensities (i) and generation interval (GI) for traits related to first lactation productive and reproductive parameters. Also comparative efficacy of the approaches were calculated.

Results: Relative efficiency of approach II over I was observed as 40.65 % more efficient. In Approach I it was found that when GI was reduced from 5.04 to 4 years, ΔG increased by roughly 26%, 26%, and 25.7 % for FL305DMY, WA, and CFI, but when GI was increased from 5.04 to 6 years, ΔG fell by 15.94%, 16%, and 15.9%. Approach II revealed that After lowering GI from 5.04 to 4 years and raising i ($p = 75$ to 70), the ΔG for 305DMY and CFI increased between 44 to 46% and WA increased between 26 to 46%, whereas GI increased from 5.04 to 6 years. The Karan Fries cattle's ΔG ranged from -2 to -16%. The current analysis suggests that in an organized herd To obtain more over 50% yearly ΔG for WA, 305DMY and CFI, the fraction of Karan of animals selected should be 70-75% and GI should be less than 5 years.

Keywords: Karan Fries, Genetic gain, Selection intensity, Generation interval.

Introduction

Any improvement in farm animals begins with selection. By selecting the best animals, the best will become parents for future generations and unwelcome animals will be culled from the herd. This further results in overall improvement of the animal in a herd. The quantity of increase in performance that is obtained through selection programs is known as genetic gain. A breeding programme's assessment of genetic gain is very important to know how genetic improvements occur in each generation. Organized mating strategies ought to be employed in order to maintain the best genetic gain (Mumtaz et al. 2021). Certain characteristics, including selection intensity or the percentage of selected animals, population variability, and heritability can be used to predict these gains. In addition to providing a bridge between theories and experiments, simulation study is used to develop and validate theories and produce guidelines for empirical experiments. The development of Karan Fries crossbred dairy cattle began in 1980 when a Holstein Friesian bull (*Bos taurus*) and a Tharparkar cow (*Bos Indicus*) were crossed followed by selection among interbreeds at ICAR-NDRI, Karnal. So far selection is being done mainly based on 305DMY due to customer expectations, the effect of output on farm profit margins, and the lack of focus when production and reproduction qualities should be given the proper weightage in the selection criteria. Although FL305MY was significantly impacted by the age at first calving (Rathee et al. 2017). Nevertheless, inefficiencies persist since higher output has had detrimental consequences on longevity, health, and reproduction (Oltenacu and Broom, 2010). Yaegboobi et al. (2011) calculated the ΔG of FL305DMY as 26.8-33.0 kg/year in HF dairy cattle. This was comparable to the approximations produced by Approaches I and II. Effa et al. (2011) estimated ΔG /year over the herd average of 1.8% for 305DMY in HF crossbred dairy cows which were comparable to the estimates obtained by Approach II (Ratwan et al. 2021). There hasn't been much research on the estimation of estimated ΔG and simulation studies for production attributes in the literature. However, there hasn't been enough research done on estimating ΔG for other performance attributes in Karan Fries cattle. This is why the current study, which evaluates the ΔG for CFI interval and 305DMY inclusion to the WA in Karan Fries cattle, was carried out for the first time in India. Utilizing several criteria, such as heritability, phenotypic standard deviation, selection differential and intensity of selection by simulating numerous elements that play a part in genetic gain estimation.

Materials and Approaches

General Evaluation of Data

Karan Fries cattle housed at the ICAR-NDRI, Karnal, Haryana, were applied in the current experiment. Data for the study were gathered from milk constituents registers, reproduction records, history-cum-pedigree sheets or registers, health and general treatment register, and calving reports upheld at the Division of Animal Genetics and Breeding, ABRC (Artificial Breeding Research Centre), and Livestock Production and Management Section. A total of 3165 lactation data from 965 cows bred by 159 sires were used. The data were collected over the course of twenty-four years, from 1993 to 2016. This study evaluated cows that had completed at least one lactation.

Data Correction

The heifers were culled based on their body conformation, health status, and age at sexual maturity. Furthermore, heifers that were unable to conceive before 40 months of age and cows with an EPA (estimated producing ability) of less than 1550 kg were also culled from the herd. Standard culling procedures are followed, and animals with low output, poor growth, bad health, congenital malformations, and breeding issues are discovered and culled on a regular basis. In this research, since there were few animals, those with fifth parity or above were clustered together. By calculating each attribute's mean and standard deviation, the data were later normalized.

Traits:

To determine the expected ΔG , two production traits - the 305DMY and the WA, and one reproductive trait - the CFI interval were considered. The 305DMY is considered to be a standard measure of production performance in dairy cattle. Genetic evaluation for the selection of sires and cows based on 305DMY is regarded as the most essential feature and is the principal characteristic for evaluating a herd's genetic progress. Most of the findings observed an increase in lactation milk yield with an increase in parity up to the third and fourth lactations (Singh et al., 2015; Dash et al., 2016).

Wet average (WA) is the most important trait for a dairy farmer. It is defined as the average daily milk supply produced by a certain cow during her lactation phase, up to 305 days or fewer. Any selection strategy adaptable at the field level should translate it into terms that can be easily understood by farmers. In this regard, wet average may strengthen dairy animal selection in the Indian environment.

CFI is an economically important feature since it evaluates the cow's capacity to resume the estrus cycle after giving birth. Furthermore, it is related to the animal's ability to conceive and get pregnant quickly following insemination (Ismael et al., 2016). It is evident from the fact that cows with a shorter CFI have higher first insemination non-return rates, higher pregnancy rates, and shorter calving intervals (Haile-Mariam et al., 2003). Following threshold linear analysis of measures of fertility in days to calving and artificial insemination data, Donoghue et al. (2004) opined that calving to first insemination is a potential measure of fertility, as the parameter estimations for this characteristic were nearly identical to those for calving success.

Eventually, observations were included up to the sixth lactation, for a total of 960, 956, and 508 for 305DMY, WA, and CFI, respectively.

Statistical Analyses

Selection in a dairy herd is primarily aimed at improving milk productivity. Therefore, genetic gain in Karan Fries herd was assessed based on of 305 DMY by distinct approaches to evaluate the net effect of selection in retrospect. The expected ΔG /generation and also ΔG /year as a result of selection of Karan Fries cattle was evaluated for first lactation additionally all lactation (Up to 6th parity) using production (FL305DMY and WA) and reproduction (CFI) by two alternative approaches. Approach I used selection differential and h^2 , while Approach II relied on the σ (phenotypic standard deviation), h^2 and p (proportion of animals selected).

Using least-squares analysis, the impact of non-genetic factors on the parameters under investigation was examined. These factors included calving season, period and age group. (Harvey

1990). Utilizing the paternal half-sib correlation approach, heritability was ascertained. (Becker 1975). First lactation production and reproductive attributes i.e. 305DMY, WA and CFI respectively were assessed in terms of expected ΔG /generation, using two distinct approaches as described by Falconer. (1981).

Approach I: $\Delta G = h^2S$, where h^2 represents trait heritability and S symbolizes the selection **Differential or Average Superiority of Chosen Parents.**

Approach II: $\Delta G = i\sigma_p h^2$; where i represents the intensity of selection, h^2 represents trait heritability and σ_p represents the trait's phenotypic standard deviation.

Here, ΔG was computed by dividing it by the generation interval in order to ascertain the expected ΔG /year in each of the two previous above-mentioned Approaches. Furthermore, ΔG /generation and ΔG /year for the aforementioned reproductive and productivity by utilizing data up to the sixth lactation, variables were computed using both techniques

Simulation Study:

Approach I simulated the GI (generation interval), which varied from the current circumstances in both directions. (increased and decreased) In approach II, i and GI were both simulated concurrently, and ΔG was calculated for various combinations.

Results and Discussion

Estimation of ΔG For First Lactation Reproduction and Production Attributes:

The total means for KF cattle demonstrate that for 305DMY, WA, and CFI, they are 3164.87 ± 31.52 kg, 10.89 ± 0.09 kg/day, and 104.01 ± 2.74 days, respectively, The phenotypic standard deviations for the first lactation WA, 305DMY, and CFI were 2.99 kg, 1070.69 kg, and 56.19 days with heritability estimates of 0.44 ± 0.01 , 0.37 ± 0.08 and 0.24 ± 0.22 , respectively for corresponding trait. Using the same data of the KF cattle, the generation interval was calculated to be 5.04 years. FL305DMY heritability estimates were found to be 0.37 ± 0.08 , revealing that FL305DMY trait is moderately heritable in Karan Fries cattle. The moderate heritability estimate, indicated that a selection can be exercised on this trait through scientific breeding programmes. The results were similar to the observations made by previous authors, who reported a heritability estimates range from low to moderate. for FL305DMY in Karan Fries cattle (Sahana and Gurnani, 2000; Nehra *et al.* 2012 and Dash 2014).

Heritability estimates of first lactation WA was obtained as 0.44 ± 0.01 indicating moderate heritability of the trait. The result was almost in conformity to the findings of Dash (2014), who reported heritability estimates of wet average as 0.40 in KF cows. Heritability estimate of CFI was 0.24 ± 0.22 . Previous researchers stated really low estimates of heritability ranging from 0.02 ± 0.008 (Berry *et al.*, 2003) to 0.13 ± 0.02 (Haile Mariam *et al.*, 2003) in HF cattle, while, Dash (2014) had reported low heritability values of 0.016 ± 0.124 and 0.06 ± 0.04 respectively, in KF cattle

In Table I, first lactation reproductive and productive features analyzed with Approach I and Approach II are presented with the ΔG /generation along and ΔG /year values.

The ΔG for FL305DMY, WA, and CFI were determined to be 20.00 kg/year, 0.41 kg/year, and 0.11 days/year, respectively, representing 0.6, 0.41, and 0.9% of the overall average by Approach I.

Approach II yielded ΔG assessments of 0.14 days/year, 1.76 kg/year and 33.7 kg/year for CFI, WA and 305 DMY respectively. These assessments translated into 1.02, 1.48, and 1.16% overall averages for the aforementioned features. Theoretically, ΔG derived by Approach I and Approach II should be the same, but in practice, they were shown to differ. This could be the result of insufficient data, which prevented the normal distribution curve assumptions required for i and σ_p in Approach II.

Yaegboobi *et al.* (2011) assessed the ΔG of FL305DMY were 26.8-33.0 kg/year in HF dairy cattle. This was similar to the estimations provided by Approach I and Approach II. Effa *et al.* (2011) ΔG of FL305DMY as 1.84 percent/year over the herd average in HF crossbred dairy cows which was similar to the estimates obtained by Approach II.

After considering the phenotypic standard deviation of the traits in addition to the degree of selection, Approach II was revealed itself to be more effective in estimating ΔG /generation and ΔG /year for first lactation production and reproduction attributes in KF cattle. Similar finding also reported by Manoj *et al.* (2023)

Table 1: Estimation of ΔG for first lactation reproduction and production attributes in Karan Fries cattle

Traits	Approach I			Approach II		
	ΔG /gen	ΔG /year	% of OA	ΔG /gen	ΔG /year	% of OA
FL305DMY (Kg)	100.8	20.00	0.6	170.2	33.7	1.02
CFI (days)	2.1	0.41	0.3	8.89	1.76	1.48
WA (Kg)	0.56	0.11	0.9	0.72	0.14	1.16

Where: Selection intensity = 0.43 and Generation Interval = 5.04 years

Approach I ($\Delta G = h^2 SD$ /Generation Interval)

Approach II ($\Delta G = i\sigma_p h^2$ / Generation Interval)

Two approaches were employed for estimation and comparison of expected ΔG and relative efficiency in KF cattle (Table 2). For FL305DMY, the expected ΔG /year was found to be 20.00 kg/year and 33.7 kg/year using Approaches I and II, respectively. Approach II was shown to be 40.65% more efficient than Approach I.

Approaches I and II yielded the expected ΔG /year of 0.10 and 0.14 kg/year for the WA,

respectively. Thus, Approach II outperforms Approach I by 28.6%.

The results of Approaches I and II showed that the ΔG /year for CFI was 0.41 and 0.90 days/year, respectively. Approach II demonstrated a higher relative efficiency than Approach I, at 61.66%

Table 2: The proportional efficacy of each approach in ΔG estimation in KF cattle

Traits	Expected ΔG /year		Superiority in efficiency (%)
	Approach I	Approach II	II over I
FL305DMY(Kg)	20.00	33.7	40.65
WA (Kg)	0.10	0.14	28.6
CFI (days)	0.41	0.90	61.66

Simulation Study

By modeling various factors involved in Approach I and II, the expected ΔG for FL305Y, WA, and CFI was calculated, to ascertain i and GI for an organized herd in order to acquire the maximum genetic gain

Expected ΔG by Approach I During Simulation

Here the GI was reduced while also being increased in order to estimate Expected ΔG . Table 3 shows the expected ΔG acquired in distinct traits for lowering (4 years) and increasing (6 years) relative to the current one (5.04).

Table 3: Simulation of GI and i for estimation of expected ΔG of production and reproduction attributes by Approach I

Trait	ΔG /gen	GI	ΔG /year	% of O.A.
305 DMY	61.01	4	25.20	0.77
		5.04	20.00	0.61
		6	16.80	0.51
WA	0.24	4	0.14	1.17
		5.04	0.11	0.93

		6	0.09	0.78
CFI	2.11	4	0.53	0.44
		5.04	0.42	0.35
		6	0.35	0.30

Approach I showed that reducing the GI from 5.04 to 4 years raised estimated ΔG by 26%, 26%, and 25.9% for FL305DMY, WA, and CFI. However, increasing the GI from 5.04 to 6 years lowered estimated ΔG by 15.94%, 16%, and 15.9%, respectively.

3.2.2 Expected ΔG by Approach II During Simulation

In Approach II, i and GI were both simulated concurrently. Table 4.1 shows the expected ΔG of FL305DMY, WA and CFI when using Approach II to simulate i and GI.

Table 4.1: Expected Genetic Gain of FL305DMY Simulating i and GI by Approach II

P (%)	i	GI	$\Delta G/\text{generation}$	$\Delta G/\text{year}$	% of O.A. average
60	0.64	4	253.38	63.34	1.93 (+88%)
65	0.57		225.66	56.42	1.72
70	0.5		197.95	49.49	1.51 (46%)
75	0.43		170.24	42.56	1.30 (44%)
80	0.35		138.57	34.64	1.06
85	0.28		110.85	27.71	0.84
90	0.2		79.18	19.80	0.60
60	0.64		5.04	253.38	50.27
65	0.57	225.66		44.77	1.36
70	0.5	197.95		39.28	1.20
75	0.43	170.24		33.78	1.03
80	0.35	138.57		27.49	0.84

85	0.28		110.85	21.99	0.67
90	0.2		79.18	15.71	0.48
60	0.64	6	253.38	42.23	1.29
65	0.57		225.66	37.61	1.15
70	0.5		197.95	32.99	1.00 (-2%)
75	0.43		170.24	28.37	0.86 (-16%)
80	0.35		138.57	23.09	0.70
85	0.28		110.85	18.48	0.56
90	0.2		79.18	13.20	0.26

$\sigma_p=1070.67$; $h^2=0.37$; O.A.3164.87kg

Table 4.2: Expected Genetic Gain of WA (wet average) on simulating i and GI by ApproachII

P (%)	i	GI	$\Delta G/\text{generation}$	$\Delta G/\text{year}$	% of O.A. average
60	0.64	4	0.77	0.19	1.59 (+86%)
65	0.57		0.75	0.19	1.56
70	0.5		0.66	0.16	1.37 (46%)
75	0.43		0.57	0.14	1.18 (26%)
80	0.35		0.46	0.12	0.96
85	0.28		0.37	0.09	0.77
90	0.2		0.26	0.07	0.55
60	0.64		0.84	0.17	1.39
65	0.57		0.75	0.15	1.24
70	0.5		0.66	0.13	1.09

75	0.43	5.04	0.57	0.11	0.94
80	0.35		0.46	0.09	0.76
85	0.28		0.37	0.07	0.61
90	0.2		0.26	0.05	0.44
60	0.64	6	0.84	0.14	1.17
65	0.57		0.75	0.12	1.04
70	0.5		0.66	0.11	0.91 (-2%)
75	0.43		0.57	0.09	0.79 (-16%)
80	0.35		0.46	0.08	0.64
85	0.28		0.37	0.06	0.51
90	0.2		0.26	0.04	0.37

$\sigma_p=2.99$ Kg; $h^2=0.44$; O.A. 10.89 kg/day

Table 4.3: Expected ΔG of CFI During i and GI Simulation Using Approach II

P (%)	i	GI	$\Delta G/\text{generation}$	$\Delta G/\text{year}$	% of O.A. average
60	0.64	4	13.22	3.31	2.78 (+88%)
65	0.57		11.78	2.94	2.47
70	0.5		10.33	2.58	2.17 (+46%)
75	0.43		8.89	2.22	1.87 (+44%)
80	0.35		7.23	1.81	1.52
85	0.28		5.79	1.45	1.22
90	0.2		4.13	1.03	0.87
60	0.64		13.22	2.62	2.21

65	0.57	5.04	11.78	2.34	1.96
70	0.5		10.33	2.05	1.72
75	0.43		8.89	1.76	1.48
80	0.35		7.23	1.44	1.21
85	0.28		5.79	1.15	0.96
90	0.2		4.13	0.82	0.69
60	0.64	6	13.22	2.20	1.85
65	0.57		11.78	1.96	1.65
70	0.5		10.33	1.72	1.45 (-2%)
75	0.43		8.89	1.48	1.24 (-16%)
80	0.35		7.23	1.21	1.01
85	0.28		5.79	0.96	0.81
90	0.2		4.13	0.69	0.58

$\sigma_p = 56.19$ days; $h^2 = 0.24$; O.A. 104.01 days

Table 4.1 shows that $\Delta G/\text{year}$ for FL305DMY increased from 19.80 to 63.34 kg/year with a rise in i (p ranges from 90% to 60%) and a GI reduction of 4 years. Similarly, expected ΔG increased from 15.71 to 50.27 kg/year with i (p ranges from 90% to 60%) and taking GI 5.04 years into consideration. However, with increase in generation interval (GI=6 years) and i ($p=60\%$ to 90%), expected $\Delta G/\text{year}$ increased only from 13.20 to 42.23 kg/year. In an organized herd, The expected ΔG for 305 DMY increased by 44 to 46% when selection intensity was increased (p ranges 70 to 75%) and GI was decreased from 5.04 to 4 years. However, in Karan fries cattle, raising the GI from 5.04 to 6 years resulted in expected ΔG ranging from -2 to -16%.

Approach II increased the $\Delta G/\text{year}$ for wet average from 0.07 to 0.19 kg/year by raising i (p ranges 90 to 60%) and decreasing GI for up to 4 years. Likewise, the expected $\Delta G/\text{year}$ raised from 0.05 to 0.17 kg/year at a selection intensity (p ranges from 90% to 60%) and GI of 5.04 years.

Table 4.2 illustrates that for an organized herd, an increase in expected ΔG for WA of 26% to 46% was obtained by decreasing GI from 5.04 to 4 years and increasing i (p ranges 75 to 70%). On the other hand, when the GI was increased from 5.04 to 6 years, the expected ΔG in Karan fries cattle varied from -2 to -16%.

Examining Table 4.3, we can see that Approach II raised $\Delta G/\text{year}$ for CFI from 1.03 to 3.37 days/year by shortening the generation interval by 4 years and increasing i (p ranges from 90% to 60%). Conversely, raising the generation interval to 5.04 years caused the expected $\Delta G/\text{year}$ to rise from 0.82 to 2.62 days/year. Nevertheless, a rise from 0.69 to 2.20 days/year was obtained by raising the generation interval to 6 years and the strength of selection (p varies from 90% to 60%). The literature was examined, but I was unable to find any that used these two Approaches to estimate genetic gain for Karan Fries cattle. However, Ratwan et al. (2021) revealed comparable results in FL305DMY, WA and CFI Sahiwal cattle, which is what I discovered in Karan Fries cattle.

Using Approach II, showed that the expected $\Delta G/\text{generation}$ and $\Delta G/\text{year}$ were higher for first lactation production and reproduction characteristics, considering the phenotypic standard deviation of the traits with the degree of selection.

Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, an organized herd of Karan fries cattle can acquire higher genetic gain annually if the generation interval (GI) are smaller than 5 years and intensity of selection (i) ranges 70–75%,

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